

Practice Abstract no. 43

Fostering collaborative platforms for data-driven solutions

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

Building on the findings of the workshop and breakout room sessions, the following recommendation and driving actions was proposed:

Recommendation: Foster collaborative platforms for data-driven solutions.

Proposed Actions:

- 1. Further facilitate and set-up multi-stakeholder platforms:** The EU holds significant expertise in fostering dialogue among diverse stakeholders. This capacity should be increased with a focused effort on food and data-driven solutions. The goal is to establish an open, collaborative dialogue platform that joins all actors in the food value chain (i.e. farmers, food companies, tech providers, researchers, policymakers, and consumers) to address current value chain gaps with relevant solutions. A key outcome of these discussions should be the identification of incentives to facilitate data sharing, which is essential to unlocking the opportunities detailed throughout this report.
- 2. Support public-private partnerships:** The EU should actively promote and implement funding mechanisms to cultivate partnerships between public sector organisations and private enterprises. This is important for facilitating the development and scaling of data-driven solutions within the food system, and can combine resources, specialised knowledge, and technological capabilities.
- 3. Organise open innovation challenges for data-driven solutions:** Open innovation challenges, such as hackathons, can drive creative, data-driven solutions to pressing problems within the food value chain. These events, often organized alongside major EU gatherings that draw large audiences, provide a collaborative framework for teams to ideate and develop, harnessing available and validated data.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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